

Quantum Kaniadakis Style versus Shannon's Entropy

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Traditionally, Shannon's spatial entropy is applied to a quantum wavefunction i.e. $(W^*(x)W(x)) \ln[W^*(x)W(x)]$. In a previous note (1), we used $W(x)f(p) \exp(ipx)$ as probability and obtained an entropy equal to: $(W^*(x)W(x)) \ln[W^*(x)W(x)] + [f^*(p)f(p)] \ln[f^*(p)f(p)] + W(x) \times d/dx W(x)$. In this note, we consider the Kaniadakis approach to entropy. For generalized statistical mechanics, Kaniadakis (2) considers $\ln[k(f(e))] = e$ from generalized scattering kinematics. He then forms the entropy as: $\int df \ln[k(f(e))]$ so that taking d/df subject to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) e_i$ returns $\ln[k(f(e))] = e$. The integral and derivative are inverse functions. In a quantum bound state, one may imagine a particle at point x . If the potential is written as a Fourier transform, different $\exp(ikx)$ exist at each x and knock the particle into different momentum states such that: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) + V(x) = E$ at each x . Thus, a scattering condition is mixed with energy for the quantum mechanical case. In other words, the Schrodinger equation is the scattering equation describing a particle's interaction with $V(x)$. Following the approach of Kaniadakis, we propose an entropy given by: $\int dW [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) + V(x)]$. To perform this integral, one must be able to write $V(x)$ in terms of $W(x)$. We consider the case of a ground state oscillator as an example. Given entropy, one may then vary it with respect to $W(x)$ subject to $EW(x)^*W(x)$ to obtain the Schrodinger equation which we argue is the generalized Kaniadakis scattering equation ((1)) for the quantum bound state.

Generalized Scattering Approach and Quantum Mechanics

Statistical mechanical distributions are often obtained by maximizing arrangements (usually written as factorials) often in phase space (subject to constraints). Maximizing arrangements is consistent with maximizing uncertainty subject to energy and particle number constraints. In a number of previous notes and in (2) it is argued that one may use scattering arguments to obtain distributions. For example, for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Taking \ln of the former and linking to the latter yields the MB distribution. For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, $f(e_1)[1 \mp f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1 \mp f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 \mp f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1 \mp f(e_2)]$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Taking \ln of the former and linking to the later yields the two distributions. The scattering approach is important because it demonstrates physical interactions which exist in a system and lead to equilibrium. Simply writing factorial arrangements may possibly be dangerous if there is no corresponding interaction mechanism. As an example, consider a quantum bound state. We argue that at point x , a particle may have momenta p with a normalized probability $f(p,x)$. If one were to maximize the number of arrangements of different p 's one would maximize:

$$\ln\{ N! / [\text{Product over } i f(p_i,x)!] \} \text{ subject to: } \sum_i p_i^2/2m f(p_i,x) = E - V(x) \quad ((2))$$

This would yield the MB distribution with an x dependent temperature: $f(p,x) = C(x) \exp(-p^2/2mT(x))$ ((3))

The problem seems to be, however, that ((3)) is consistent with two particle scattering $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and not with one particle scattering from a potential which itself may be written as a Fourier series in $\exp(ikx)$ such that an $\exp(ikx)$ acting on an $\exp(ipx)$ yields an $\exp((p+k)x)$. This is a very different scattering scenario from that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and leads to different statistics (except for the ground state of a harmonic oscillator). Thus, we argue that a scattering equation for a quantum bound state is actually given by the Schrodinger equation written as:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)] + V(x) = E \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{Or } -1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((4b)) \quad \hbar=1$$

We argue that ((4b)) demonstrates scattering between a particle and $V(x)$ if one writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series i.e.

$$V(x)W(x) = [\text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx)] [\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)]$$

Different $\exp(ikx)$ combine with $\exp(ipx)$, demonstrating scattering, but at the same time $V(x)W(x)$ is related to potential energy because of $V(x)$ and needs to be combined with average kinetic energy at x to obtain a conservation of energy equation.

Kaniadakis Entropy

In (2), Kaniadakis suggests that generalized statistics may be described by general dynamics i.e.

$$\text{Ln}[k(f(e))] = (e-u)/T \quad ((5)) \quad (u \text{ is the chemical potential})$$

Here $f(e)$ is the distribution (particle number) and k is a function related to dynamics. For the MB case $k=1$, but for the FD case $k=f(e)/[1-f(e)]$ and for the BE $k=f(e)/[1+f(e)]$.

To obtain the Kaniadakis entropy, the LHS of ((5)) is integrated over df so that the inverse operation d/df yields the LHS of ((5)) once again. The right hand side is obtained by taking d/df of energy and particle number constraints. Thus:

$$\text{Integral phase space} \quad \text{Integral } df \quad \text{Ln}[k(f(e))] \quad ((6)) \text{ yields Kaniadakis entropy.}$$

For the FD and BE cases, one may see that the Kaniadakis entropy is identical with that given in statistical mechanics texts using the maximization of factorial approaches subject to energy and particle number constraints (3).

As a result, one should be able to use the bound state scattering equation analogous to ((5)) to obtain a quantum entropy. We suggest that the time independent Schrodinger equation is the one analogous to ((5)).

Kaniadakis Quantum Entropy

For the bound state, we suggest that:

Quantum bound state Kaniadakis entropy density = $\int dW(x) [-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x)W(x)]$

This is analogous to a Lagrangian type of problem in which one varies a function $W(x)$ and one has derivatives of this function (as in field theory).

$$\text{Kaniadakis entropy density} = -1/4m (d/dx W)^2 + \int dW V(x)W(x) \quad ((7))$$

where $V(x)$ must be expressed in terms of $W(x)$.

Taking d/dW of ((7)) subject to the constraint $b1 W(x)W(x)$ yields the Schrodinger equation if $b1=E/2$. This is a little different from usual variational approaches of obtaining the Schrodinger equation which vary $W^*(x)$.

Alternatively, the RHS of the Schrodinger equation is EW so:

$$\text{Kaniadakis entropy density} = \int dW E W = .5 E W^*W$$

As an example, consider the harmonic oscillator for which $V(x)=.5k x^*x$. For the ground state $W(x)= C \exp(-bx^*x)$ so $V(x)= -(.5k /b) \ln(W/C)$ where $b=\text{sqrt}(km)/2$ and $C= (\text{sqrt}(km)/3.14)^{.25}$
(4)

$$\text{Let } .5k x^*x = A \ln(W) + B \quad ((8)) \quad \text{where } A=\text{sqrt}(k/m) \quad B= .25\text{sqrt}(km) \ln[\text{sqrt}(km)/3.14]$$

Then:

$$\text{Quantum oscillator ground state Kaniadakis entropy density} = -1/4m (d/dx W)^2 + \int dW [A W \ln(W) + B W]$$

From ((8)), $kx = A/W dW/dx$ so

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Kaniadakis entropy density for the oscillator gs} &= -k/(2m) (W/A)^2 [A \ln W + B] + BW^2/2 + \\ &A.5[W^*W \ln W - .5 W^*W] \\ &= -.25 \text{sqrt}(k/m) W^*W \quad ((9)) \end{aligned}$$

This is essentially the spatial density multiplied by ground state energy multiplied by $-.5$.

Thus, for all cases, the Kaniadakis quantum bound state entropy is $.5E W^*W$.

[An alternative approach to solving the problem for the ground state oscillator is to use: $.5kx^2 = A \ln W + B$ ((10)) and take d/dx twice to obtain an expression for $d/dx d/dx W$ in terms of $dW/dx * dW/dx$. One may use ((10)) to write $dW/dx * dW/dx$ as $2Wk/A + 4x^2 W^*W k^2k / (WA^2A)$. This may be integrated as $\int dW d/dx d/dx W$, but yields the same result as above.]

Comparison with Shannon's Approach

Shannon's entropy formula is often applied to the spatial wavefunction $W(x)$. Thus, one often sees in the literature $W^*W \ln[W^*W]$ as the spatial entropy of a wavefunction. In (1), we suggest using $\text{Probability}(p,x) = W(x)f(p) \exp(ipx)$. Applying Shannon's approach yields:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy density} = [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] + [fp^*fp] \ln[fp^*fp] + W(x) \times d/dx W(x) \quad ((11))$$

This seems to differ from the Kaniadakis approach result, although for the ground state oscillator the phase space integral of the first term is related to potential energy and the second to kinetic energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Schrodinger time independent equation is equivalent to Kaniadakis generalized kinematics equation $\ln[k(f(e))] = (e-u)/T$ for the quantum bound state case. Kaniadakis integrates the LHS of this equation over df to obtain an entropy. If one integrates the Schrodinger equation over dW (so that d/dW of this entropy together with the d/dW of the constraint $b1 W^*W$ yields the Schrodinger equation) one obtains the usual spatial quantum entropy for the ground state of an oscillator together with a second term proportional to W^*W . This approach seems to yield an entropy which is similar to a Lagrangian with a function and derivatives of the function (as used in field theory). We find:

$$\text{Kaniadakis entropy density} = -1/4m (d/dx W)^2 + \int dW V(x)W(x)$$

where one may write $V(x)$ as a function of $W(x)$. Alternatively, one may write:

$$\text{Kaniadakis entropy density} = \int dW E W = .5 E W^*W \text{ for all } V(x).$$

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, integrated over phase space yields $1/T E - 1/T \ln(C)$ where C is a normalization constant, thus entropy is closely linked to energy.

References

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